

A Study on Consumer Behaviour of Egg in India

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Abstract

The present study focuses on buyer behaviour in Egg market and offers suggestions for the increase of egg consumption, which plays a pivotal role for the survival of the poultry Industry. The aim of marketing is to identify and satisfy target customers' needs and wants. Marketers must study their target customers wants, perceptions, preferences, and shopping and buying behaviour. Such a study will provide clues for developing new products, product features, prices, channels, messages and other marketing mix elements. It is very important for marketing and future marketers to recognize why and how individuals make their consumption decisions so that they can make better marketing decisions. No doubt, marketers who understand buyer behaviour have a great competitive advantage in the market place

Key words: Consumer Behaviour, Egg, Marketing

Introduction

The most egg consumption and manufacturing occur in Asia's densely inhabited regions, where this protein acts as a fantastic food. In this region, there is a wide range of production, processing, and pricing for eggs and egg products. This region is made up of 16 countries, each with its own culture, religion, welfare system, eating customs, and so on. Another difference between these countries is their level of industrial activity. There are clear variances in egg prices across the region as a result of feed, production methods, and efficiency in production.

Consumers gives dually importance on a balanced diet, brand consciousness, higher education levels,healthfulness,superior quality ,convenience and valued animal welfare are certain

factors through which consumers are decided whether they buy the egg products or not. There are lots of factors which affects the choices of consumer like

- Environmental factors
- Cultural factors
- Consumer taste and preferences
- Income level of consumer
- Buying behaviour
- Price of the product

Material and methods

With the conceptual background, an attempt was made to study the consumer behaviour in egg market in the area under study covering various socio-economic factors – income of the consumer, family size, food habits, occupational pattern, etc., which influence the purchasing pattern of the consumers. The views of consumer over prices and sources of price information are examined

Result and Discussion

Industry and retailers, who wish to succeed in food category. They would do well if they understand these factors and strengthen the food products, which they are offering to their customers. According to survey conducted, for large section of respondents, taste and nutrition are the most important factors while shopping for food. 40% of the respondents consider cost of food important. While purchase food, people are not keen about convenience of purchasing food. It is seen that 100% of respondents buy nutritionally enriched food to stay healthy whereas other important reasons are for children and to avoid medical treatment. Factors such as maintaining attractiveness, interest, curiosity, retarding age are not encouraging them to buy nutritionally enriched food. In the survey, a correlation was found between the lifestyle changes to increase nutritionally enriched food in the diet with the gender, age & qualification of the respondents.

There is a growing concern that many Indians are going through an unbalanced diet due to lifestyle changes which has led to health problems with increasing age. Respondents are ready to change their lifestyle by increasing consumption of nutritionally enriched food, irrespective of their age. However, the acceptance of lifestyle change is found to be more in the age group of 40-60 than 21-40. A diet built on nutrient-dense foods can provide a solid foundation for better health. The shift to positive nutrition guidance and education based on a consistently determined standardized nutrient density index or score can help people implement the lifestyle changes. From the study it is also seen that education of respondents affect the decision regarding lifestyle change

to increase consumption of nutritionally enriched food. Such acceptance of is found to be more in respondents with post graduate degree.

Conclusion

Egg is the most cost-effective source of protein; the rural or low-income population consumes the most poultry meat. The focus might be on building quality brands and creating a revolution by selling highest quality chicken meat, meat products and eggs to the country's most remote areas at a competitive price. It is not only the business, but also the style of doing business that will determine the future success of an enterprise.

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